

RM ROADMAP

D2.2 Catalogue of existing professional development opportunities

This document provides an overview of existing professional development opportunities targeting Research Managers (RMs). Five categories were defined to collect the data mainly focused on opportunities targeting RMs: Training, Mobility, Networking, Funding opportunities, and RM Networks.

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“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Project acronym

RM-ROADMAP

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List of Abbreviations

ASTP	Association of European Science and Technology Transfer Professionals
EARMA	European Association of Research Managers and Administrators
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Research Management / Research Manager

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Summary

One of RM-ROADMAP's main objectives is to inform the community about existing training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities. A [preliminary report](#) has already been delivered by NOVA, presenting the initial results of this mapping exercise to get an overview of existing professional development opportunities targeting Research Managers (RMs). The mapping is now completed and a catalogue was produced (Annex 3) which gathers and collates all the mapped information on existing training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities, as well as on the currently existing RM Networks, rendering it a useful resource to be used by the RM community. Making all this information available to RMs in Europe and beyond increases awareness about existing opportunities that can help in their professional development, as well as contributing to making RMs feel part of a crucial community that fosters research in Europe and contributes to strengthening the European Research Area (ERA). The information contained in this catalogue will also be widely disseminated to the RM community through an open online tool, developed in collaboration with the parallel EU Project CARDEA.

The information in the catalogue will be complemented with an analysis of the professional development needs of the RM community obtained through an EU-survey, developed under the RM-ROADMAP project in coordination with WP1. Future professional development schemes will also be discussed with the RM community in a co-creation exercise to address the needs of the community and the gaps identified in this mapping. The entire analysis, as well as future recommendations, will be presented in the final report due in June 2025.

Four categories of opportunities targeting RMs were defined to collect the data: training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities. A fifth category was later added, RM Networks, as they often provide a combination of the aforementioned activities.

This document is structured in seven sections as follows:

Section 1) introduces the RM-ROADMAP project and work package 2 (WP2);

Section 2) provides background notes about the skills and competencies of Research Managers;

Section 3) provides details on the methodology to collect data via the mapping exercise;

Section 4) showcases the main results of the mapping exercise on the professional development opportunities;

Section 5) describes the challenges encountered in collecting, organising and analysing the data;

Section 6) provides a first set of conclusions and recommendations;

Section 7) contains references used in the production of this document.

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In addition, this document includes three annexes: i) the concept note, describing the planned activities for WP2, ii) the online template used to collect the information, and iii) the catalogue - which is the main output of the mapping exercise - a user-friendly list of opportunities collected until July 2024, organised by type and geographical scope.

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1. Introduction and aim

1.1. About the RM-ROADMAP project

RM-ROADMAP charts a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support its delivery. Conducted over 36 months, the project is funded to the amount of €1.5m by the European Commission Horizon Europe funding programme.

The overarching objective of RM-ROADMAP is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

RM-ROADMAP allows existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform consultation process in research management. This co-creation process gathers the existing communities and expands them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners are working together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HÉTFA Research Institute (Hungary); NOVA University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

For the implementation of the project, the following Work Packages were designed:

WP	Work Package name	Lead partner	Deliverables
WP1	Intelligence	HETFA	D1.1 - Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape D1.2 - Report on ERA-wide landscape
WP2	Training and Development	NOVA	D2.1 - Preliminary report on professional development opportunities D2.2 - Catalogue of professional development opportunities D2.3 - Report on the professional development opportunities

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WP3	Roadmap and Advocacy	EARMA	<p>D3.1 - Short policy brief 1</p> <p>D3.2 - Overarching Roadmap Plan</p> <p>D3.3 - Short policy brief 2</p> <p>D3.4 - Overarching Roadmap</p>
WP4	Community, Communication and Dissemination	Crowdhelix	<p>D4.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan</p> <p>D4.2 - Online Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP)</p> <p>D4.3 - Activity report on KCP and DCE</p> <p>D4.4 - Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report</p> <p>D4.5 - Activity Report on Knowledge and Community Platform</p> <p>D4.6 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report</p>
WP5	Project Management	EARMA	<p>D5.1 - Quality Management Plan</p> <p>D5.2 - Data Management Plan</p> <p>D5.3 - First management and coordination report</p> <p>D5.4 - Final management and coordination report</p>
WP6	Sustainability and Exploitation	ASTP	<p>D6.1 - Sustainability Plan</p> <p>D6.2 - Final sustainability report</p>

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1.2. Work Package 2 - Training and Development

The overall objective of WP2 is to map existing training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities available to the Research Management community across Europe, collect these opportunities in a catalogue, showcase the opportunities available in an open online tool developed in collaboration with the CARDEA project, as well as foster collaboration, exchange of resources and best practices between the RM trainers and communities of practice.

For that, the following tasks were defined:

- Task 2.1 - Assessing the current training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities for the RM community & co-creating in collaboration with the CARDEA project an open smart database.
- Task 2.2 - Producing survey, gap analysis, and recommendations to fulfil the identified training and networking needs.
- Task 2.3 - Fostering the creation of communities of practice among trainers.
- Task 2.4 - Fostering national and thematic communities (in Widening Countries) including research infrastructure: RM community incubator.

For a complete overview of the WP2 tasks, activity plan, and calendarization, please explore WP2 Concept Note in Annex 1. This concept paper acts as a thorough blueprint, offering a distinct structure and rules for all parties engaged in putting WP2 into action.

Task 2.1, titled "Assessing the current training, networking, mobility, and funding per segment of the RM community & creating an open smart database," led to the development of this Catalogue showcasing the work developed by NOVA (leaders of WP2) in collaboration with the WP2 partners ASTP, EARMA, CHX, JANSSEN, and UNAE, and with the input of all the other RM-ROADMAP partner institutions.

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2. Background

2.1. Research Managers (RMs) within the R&I Ecosystem

The research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem has experienced significant growth over recent decades, offering numerous opportunities for research funding, transnational cooperation, networking, and mobility. This expansion has created a competitive environment and increased the demand for skilled professionals in science, technology, and innovation management, communication, and policy assessment. To maximise the potential of R&I at various levels, both excellent researchers and highly skilled professionals are needed. These professionals work in research administration, management, knowledge transfer, science communication, research governance, and policy (Oliveira et al., 2022, p.6). They are known as Research Managers (RMs), who collaborate with researchers within common working ecosystems.

RMs play crucial roles throughout the research lifecycle. Upstream, they attract and advocate for obtaining research funding, define strategies, and establish partnerships across various sectors. During research, they support activities such as post-award management, technological platform management, ethical compliance, and intellectual property management. Downstream, RMs enhance the impact of research through outreach, science communication, and facilitating societal benefits in areas such as education, culture, social welfare, economy, public policy, health, and the environment (Agostinho et al., 2018), to name but a few. They also address cross-cutting issues like responsible research, innovation, gender, diversity, inclusion, and ethics.

To fully realise the potential of the R&I's ecosystem at all levels, the Council of the European Union emphasised the need to amplify access to research and innovation excellence across the Union in its 2021 document (Council of the European Union, 2021). The Council recognised the need to strengthen the strategic capabilities of Europe's public research organisations and launched ERA Action 17 for 2022-2024. This initiative aims to improve the European R&I system by involving at least 100 public research-performing and funding organisations by the end of 2024, fostering cooperation in Science Management. Moreover, the Council's Recommendation on a European framework to attract and retain research, innovation and entrepreneurial talents in Europe officially recognises Research Management as a career profession.

ERA Action 17 organises workshops with stakeholder groups, member states, and associate countries' representatives to gather expectations and recommendations. A key challenge is upskilling Research Managers to enhance their competencies, keep them informed about training and mobility opportunities, and ensure high-quality training and mobility.

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2.2. Research Managers: main skills and competencies

According to ESCO (European Commission, s.d.), “Research Managers oversee the research and development functions of a research facility or program or university. They support the executive staff, coordinate work activities, and monitor staff and research projects. They may work in a wide array of sectors, such as the chemical, technical and life sciences sectors. Research Managers can also advise on research and execute research themselves.”

Some of the essential skills that ESCO lists are: coping with challenging demands; discussing research proposals; estimating duration of work; managing budgets; managing research and development projects; managing staff; performing scientific research; providing project information [...]; reporting analysis results; respecting cultural differences [...]; studying a collection; studying topics; working independently [...] (adapted from ESCO website; 10.07.2024).

In the last few decades, the responsibilities of Research Managers have expanded significantly to include a variety of interrelated tasks (Agostinho, et al., 2018) and they are now expected to manoeuvre through a challenging environment while juggling several factors and adjusting to shifting conditions. Successful professionals must have a multi-talented and mission-oriented personality (Shambrook & Roberts, 2011). RMs must also have a wide range of skills and knowledge to support high-quality research (Green and Langley, 2009).

Moreover, as studies conducted in recent years have shown (e.g. Virágh et al., 2020, and Davis-Hamilton & Marina, 2018), the emergence of new challenges and opportunities means that RMs must be willing to remain lifelong learners, must adapt to continuous change, and integrate competencies to reflect these changes, including a wide range of transferable skills such as **reliability, efficiency, flexibility, planning and strategic thinking, team building, and motivation building, attention to detail, problem-solving skills, pressure and multitasking skills, communication, and organisational skills.**

In 2024, the CARDEA-Research Managers Open Research Doors ([CARDEA](#)) project produced a [report](#) containing an *RM Comp-A Competence Based Approach for Research Manager Career Development in the European Research Area* with the competence profile of RMs. The results indicate that “In the context of the role of Research Manager, cognitive abilities generally refer to a set of transferable skills that are relevant across various tasks and situations. These skills are often considered essential for effective leadership, management, and collaboration in diverse and dynamic environments, including research. Also known as transversal skills, they contribute to overall professional success and adaptability” (O’Regan, M. K. & Saporito, P., 2024, page 13).

Also, “The diversity of roles within research management requires an adaptable competence framework that can accommodate a multitude of profiles of research management professionals working in different institutional and national contexts.

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There is a need for a European competence framework that acknowledges the diverse tasks and duties undertaken by Research Managers. Such a framework should allow for flexibility while providing a common foundation that ensures consistency and recognition of the role's significance across the ERA." (O'Regan, M. K. & Saporito, P., 2024, page 7). In the RM-ROADMAP project, WP1 specifically addresses these challenges by assessing skills and competencies needed for Research Managers, while WP2 cross-references them with the professional development activities currently available for the community. For a comprehensive literature review on skills and competencies see WP1 deliverable D1.1 Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape.

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3. Methodology

In order to understand what professional development opportunities currently exist for RMs in Europe, a mapping exercise was conducted, collecting specific data on training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities available. The information which is now gathered, organised and collated in a Catalogue of opportunities will be disseminated and made available through an online dashboard developed in collaboration with CARDEA.

We have also collected data on RM networks, as these will be helpful to map further training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities, while being a testimonial to the overall development, awareness-raising and professionalisation of RM.

The exercise actively engaged the network of the project's ambassadors, both national and thematic. They contributed with information on opportunities available in their own countries or related to their specific area of expertise and have also contributed to validate the information previously collected.

The following steps were undertaken:

1. Stocktaking of existing online tools for disseminating training, networking, mobility and/ or funding opportunities to support the **identification of the main data entries** and types of information to be mapped.

2. Definition of the scope of the mapping of the training, mobility, networking and funding opportunities for Research Managers:

- **Definition of Research Managers:** the definition of Research Managers (RM) in the current mapping covers the different areas of specialisation of these professionals working in both Research Performing Organizations, Research Funding Organizations, and other (private companies, NGOs), including (but not limited to) such tasks as:
 - pre-award
 - post-award
 - innovation
 - science communication
 - outreach/community
 - impact
 - ethics
 - policy
 - infrastructure
 - data management
 - research assessment

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- researcher development/ talent development
 - lab management
- **Type of opportunities for professional development:** The following categories were defined:
- **Training activities:** Training courses, modules, degrees, programmes, etc.
 - **Mobility opportunities:** Opportunities that can enable RMs to move between institutions, spend time working on different contexts, learning from and exchanging experiences with their counterparts.
 - **Networking activities:** Activities may include training and mobility, but the main aim is to provide networking opportunities for the participants. For example, annual meetings of the RM associations, conferences targeted to RM-related topics, thematic groups, etc.
 - **Funding schemes:** Funding programmes or opportunities that support RM professional development, such as mobility programmes, support to participate in events (such as conferences) or in training, open applications for projects targeted to RM topics, etc.
 - **Research Managers Networks:** Formal and informal associations, platforms, and communities of practice. With thematic groups that are part of an association being included in the networking opportunities.
- **Inclusion criteria:** The following criteria were considered for inclusion,
- Targeted to Research Managers (RM);
 - Frequent opportunities (in opposition to one-off activities that may not be available in the future);
 - Open for participation (as opposed to opportunities only open to RMs from a particular institution).
- **Exclusion criteria:** The following criteria were considered for exclusion,
- Info sessions about specific funding calls/programmes;
 - Non-regular training sessions;
 - Institutional internal training not available for external participants.

3. Creation of an online template (Annex 2) to collect training, networking, and mobility data, as well as funding opportunities and RM networks.

4. Validating the data protection procedures to put in place regarding data collection (in alignment with the project's data management plan).

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5. Mapping the institutions responsible for providing training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities, at the EU and national levels through desk research.

6. Inviting institutions to fill in the online template (Annex 2)The mapping took place between April 2023 and July 2024.

7. Control and validate the data provided by the institutions.

8. Finalising and Implementing Terminology Adjustments for the RM Careers Matrix Framework

Given that the CARDEA project is currently developing a Matrix Framework for RM Careers, which establishes career stages spanning from RM1 to RM4, a final adjustment of terminology has been implemented. Consequently, both the Catalogue and the online tool (developed in coordination with CARDEA) now utilise this standardised terminology.

WP 2 Initial terminology	CARDEA
Beginners (1-2 years experience)	RM 1 First Stage Research Manager
Early-career (2-5 years experience)	RM 2 Recognised Research Manager
Mid-level (5-8 years experience)	RM 3 Established Research Manager
Senior (>8 years experience)	RM 4 Senior Research Manager

For a full description of the different profiles, please check the [CARDEA Matrix Framework](#).

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4. Results and analysis

All the professional development opportunities mapped within WP2 are available in the **RM-ROADMAP Catalogue of Professional Development Opportunities for Research Managers in Europe** in Annex 3. The following section presents an analysis, highlighting key trends and identifying gaps in professional development opportunities, with a particular focus on the distribution of opportunities by type of opportunity, geographical scope, RM professional areas, and levels of experience.

Distribution of opportunities by type

A total of 335 professional development opportunities targeting Research Managers were collected through this mapping exercise, spanning 39 European countries. The data reveals that more than half of the opportunities (51.04%) fall under training activities (n=171), highlighting a strong emphasis on training within the field of research management. By contrast, mobility opportunities (n=9) and Funding Schemes (n=11) constitute 2.69% and 3.28% of the total opportunities, respectively. Following training, RM Networks represent 30.15% (n=101) of the professional development opportunities, while networking activities account for 12.84% (n=43).

Figure 1- Number of professional development opportunities per type

The predominance of training activities underscores the sector's focus on skill enhancement and knowledge acquisition. This finding suggests that there is a demand for structured learning experiences, which are being actively addressed through a variety of training programs and courses.

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On the other hand, across the board, there is a noticeable scarcity of mobility and funding opportunities. For example, Switzerland, Poland, Malta, Italy, Germany and Croatia are the only countries mapped that specifically have mobility schemes for their Research Managers. Funding opportunities promoted at a national level are limited to Albania, Croatia, Italy and Netherlands (regardless of the geographical scope of the mobility). This relatively low percentage of mobility and funding opportunities points to potential areas for growth and improvement.

Mobility opportunities, which are crucial for fostering international collaboration and the exchange of best practices, are notably underrepresented. This scarcity may limit Research Managers' ability to gain diverse, cross-border experiences that are vital for their professional growth and the advancement of the research management field.

Similarly, the limited availability of funding schemes highlights a critical gap. Funding is essential to enable Research Managers to participate in conferences, workshops, and other professional development activities without financial constraints. The lack of such opportunities can create obstacles to the continuous professional development and networking efforts of many Research Managers, particularly those from institutions with limited resources.

The significant presence of RM Networks (30.15%) reflects the importance of community building and collaboration within the research management profession. These networks provide platforms for knowledge sharing, mentorship, and the collective advancement of the profession. They play a pivotal role in building a cohesive and supportive professional community, which is essential for addressing common challenges and fostering innovation. For example, Italy (n=11) and Spain (n=10), as well as Belgium (n=7), France (n=7), United Kingdom (n=7) and Germany (n=6) show a strong presence of RM networks, which are crucial for fostering community and collaboration among Research Managers. Moreover, there is a notable positive correlation (0.47) between countries with a higher number of RM Networks and the availability of training opportunities. Except for Italy, the aforementioned countries rank among the top 10 in terms of available training opportunities. This correlation can be attributed to the fact that these networks often play a direct role in providing training opportunities or supporting their members in accessing them, thereby enhancing professional development and career progression within the field.

Additionally, the overall significant number of RM Networks may indicate the proactiveness of a community that faces limited funding and mobility opportunities for career progression, since many RM Networks result from bottom-up approaches.

Networking activities, comprising 12.84% of the opportunities, further emphasise the value placed on professional connections and the exchange of ideas. These activities facilitate the creation of valuable professional relationships, which can lead to collaborations, career advancements, and the dissemination of best practices.

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Geographical Scope of Professional Development Opportunities

The different opportunities have been categorised, in terms of geographical coverage, as National, when available within a country; European, when they are accessible in more than one country and their focus is on Europe; International, in cases where their focus goes beyond Europe.

According to this classification, a majority of the opportunities are targeted at the national level, comprising 62.09% (n=208) of the total. European-level opportunities account for 16.72% (n=56), while 21.49% (n=72) are available at an international level, beyond Europe.

The dominance of professional development opportunities targeting national RMs suggests that many countries have established national frameworks and resources dedicated to the professional development of Research Managers. The high number of RM Networks (n=89) and training activities (n=90) at the national level further underscores the emphasis on local support structures for skill development and community building within individual countries.

Figure 2 - Professional Development Opportunities by geographical scope

Further analysis of the data reveals the diverse sources of these opportunities. At the national level (n=208), the majority of training activities (n=90) are offered by universities or research performing organisations (n=47), followed by RM networks (n=22). Public administration entities related to governmental or funding agencies account for only 11 opportunities, while private consultancies, which have been growing in recent years, organise 14 opportunities. The remaining opportunities are

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provided by other types of institutions.

At the European level (n=56), training activities (n=23) are distributed among private consultancies (n=11), universities or research performing institutions (n=8), and NGOs or other types of institutions, including those related to specific projects. This distribution indicates a balanced contribution from various sectors, fostering a collaborative environment for professional development across Europe.

At the international level (n=72), training activities are predominantly organised by universities or research performing organisations (n=24), followed by RM associations (n=19) and private consultancies (n=10). Other types of institutions account for the remaining opportunities.

The data indicates that a substantial majority of professional development opportunities are available at the national level. This dominance suggests that many opportunities are organised at an institutional level, such as by universities or research performing organisations, as well as by RM networks themselves. These networks, often relying on internal volunteers, play a crucial role in developing and offering these activities. The high number of RM Networks (n=89) and training activities (n=90) at the national level underscore the importance of local support structures and the initiative of individual institutions and networks in fostering professional development.

In contrast, European-level opportunities, while fewer in number, place a notable emphasis on networking activities (n=15) and mobility opportunities (n=9). This pattern highlights the importance of cross-border collaboration and the exchange of best practices within Europe, partly due to the needs and nature of the RM tasks. Such opportunities facilitate broader professional networking and exposure to diverse research management practices, which are crucial for the professional growth of Research Managers.

International opportunities, though comprising just over a fifth of the total, are predominantly focused on training activities (n=58). This focus indicates a strong global interest in developing the skills and competencies of Research Managers, reflecting the universal nature of many research management challenges. The existence of international training opportunities suggests an ongoing effort to standardise training programs that can address common issues faced by Research Managers worldwide.

Overall, the distribution of professional development opportunities by geographical scope highlights distinct patterns in the availability and focus of these opportunities. The predominance of national-level opportunities reflects the proactive efforts of institutions and RM networks in supporting professional development, despite often limited resources. Meanwhile, the European and international levels emphasise networking, mobility, and training, facilitating broader collaboration and knowledge exchange. A better understanding of these diverse patterns, especially when considering limited funding or fewer mobility opportunities could significantly enhance the

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comprehensive development of Research Managers, fostering a more interconnected and well-supported professional community across Europe and beyond.

The national level

Following the analysis of the geographical distribution of professional development opportunities, we now turn our attention to the specific professional development activities organised at the national level. The total number of professional development opportunities is displayed on the EU map below (Figure 3), which provides insight into the support structures available for Research Managers at the national level.

It is important to note that the team responsible for the mapping exercise is based in Portugal. Consequently, there may be a bias in the number of mapped activities within Portugal due to the team's extensive knowledge and access to local institutions and opportunities. This potential bias should be considered when interpreting the data. Despite strong dissemination efforts, we are faced with the possibility that the effectiveness of the dissemination of the online mapping template in each individual country was different due to unidentified causes; the analysis should thus be taken cautiously.

Figure 3 - Professional development opportunities targeting national RM communities

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The data shows Portugal and Germany with the highest number of professional development opportunities (n=27), followed by the United Kingdom (n=26), Switzerland (n=18), Spain (n=18) and Italy (n= 15). However, it is important to note that the data may reflect a potential bias regarding the Portuguese data, as explained above. When examining the variety of professional development opportunities, Germany, the United Kingdom, Switzerland and Italy demonstrate a robust framework for supporting Research Managers. These countries provide a comprehensive set of opportunities that address various professional development needs, including training activities, RM networks, networking, and mobility opportunities. In Germany, the majority of these opportunities are training activities (n=15), supplemented by networking activities (n=5), RM networks (n=6), and one mobility opportunity targeting RM at national level. Similarly, in the United Kingdom, training activities (n=15), RM networks (n=7) and networking opportunities (n=3) dominate the landscape, with one mobility also available. Switzerland has a strong focus on training activities (n=9), complemented by RM networks (n=2) and networking activities (n=6), also with one targeted mobility scheme. Italy also shows a high level of professional development activities with a substantial number of RM Networks opportunities (n=11), also including 2 training activities and one mobility scheme.

On the opposite spectrum, other EU countries show minimal professional development activities. For instance, Estonia, Georgia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, and Romania each have only one mapped opportunity, indicating a need for enhanced support and resources in these countries. This trend is also evident in specific EU regions:

- **The Balkans:** Countries like Albania (n=6), Bosnia and Herzegovina (n=5), Croatia (n= 5), Hungary (n=4), North Macedonia (n=4), Serbia (n=4), Slovenia (n=4) and Montenegro (n=3), to name a few, display relatively few opportunities, suggesting a gap in the support available for Research Managers in this region. This lack of opportunities may hinder the professional growth of Research Managers in the region.
- **Northern Europe:** The region offers a moderate number of opportunities across Norway (n=9), Denmark (n=7), Finland (n=6), and Iceland (n=3). Further insights are needed to interpret this pattern.
- **Southern Europe:** Countries such as Italy (n=15), Spain (n=18), and Portugal (n=27) show a high number of opportunities, reflecting strong support structures. However, Greece (n=2) and Malta (n=4) have fewer opportunities, indicating potential areas for improvement in this region.

It is important to relate this data to the professional development opportunities available at the European and international levels. The mapping exercise identified numerous opportunities at these broader levels, which could potentially benefit Research Managers in countries with scarce national resources. European-level opportunities (n=56) and international opportunities (n=72) offer additional avenues for training, networking, and mobility that can enhance professional development.

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However, several challenges exist for Research Managers from resource scarce countries to participate in these opportunities. Financial constraints, lack of institutional support, lack of reserved time for training, and limited access to information about these opportunities can hinder participation. Moreover, language barriers and logistical issues, such as visa requirements, can further complicate the ability of Research Managers to engage in European and international professional development activities.

Addressing these challenges is crucial. Providing financial support, increasing awareness of opportunities through targeted outreach, and facilitating easier access to mobility programs can help bridge gaps. If a more inclusive approach is fostered, Research Managers from all regions can benefit from the diverse array of professional development opportunities available at both European and international levels.

Participation costs

Another important aspect of accessibility to professional development opportunities is the cost associated with participation. The data reveals significant differences in the availability of free versus paid professional development activities. It is important to note that funding opportunities and RM networks were excluded from this analysis, the former because they do not require payment for participation and the latter due to the fact that limited information on cost was available for RM networks.

Figure 4 - Distribution of Professional Development Opportunities by Type and Cost

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The data indicates that a significant proportion of professional development opportunities are not free, with 69.23% (n=153) requiring payment, while only 30.77% (n=68) are free. This cost can be a barrier that limits the access for Research Managers, particularly those from countries with limited financial resources.

Differences by Type of Activity

- **Training Activities:** Training activities are predominantly not free, with 133 out of 171 training opportunities (77.78%) requiring payment. Only 36 training activities (21.05%) are free of charge. This cost barrier for training can be a significant obstacle for Research Managers seeking to enhance their skills and knowledge.
- **Mobility Opportunities:** Mobility opportunities present a more balanced cost structure, with 6 out of 9 opportunities (66.67%) being free and 3 (33.33%) requiring payment. This suggests that mobility programs are relatively more accessible in financial terms, which is encouraging for facilitating international collaboration and exchange.
- **Networking Activities:** Networking activities also show a favourable cost distribution, with 26 out of 43 opportunities (62.22%) being free and 17 (37.78%) requiring payment. This relatively high percentage of free networking activities is beneficial as it promotes community building and professional connections without significant financial barriers.

Professional Development Opportunities for different RM areas

The analysis of professional development opportunities targeting specific Research Management (RM) areas reveals important trends and gaps across various domains. The following data presents the distribution of these opportunities across different RM areas, highlighting the most relevant information.

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RM areas	Training activity	Mobility opportunity	Networking activity	Funding scheme	RM Networks	Total
Data management	41	3	27	7	55	133
Ethics	38	5	26	5	47	121
Impact	70	5	28	8	36	147
Infrastructure	12	3	20	7	20	62
Innovation	57	5	26	9	62	159
Lab management	7	2	14	8	17	48
Leading a team / office	44	4	16	7	38	109
Outreach/community	33	3	28	7	23	94
Policy	65	4	35	6	69	179
Post-award	108	9	28	7	48	200
Pre-award	78	9	25	8	43	163
Research assessment	12	5	22	5	21	65
Researcher development/Talent development	36	4	21	7	50	118
Science communication	52	4	28	8	24	116

Figure 5 - Number of professional development opportunities for different RM areas

The post-award area stands out with the highest number of professional development opportunities (n=200), followed by the policy (n=179) and pre-award areas (n=163). This indicates a strong focus on the management of funded research and the processes leading up to securing research funding. In these areas, training activities dominate, with post-award (n=108) and pre-award (n=78) displaying significant numbers. In the policy area, networking activities (n=35) slightly outnumber training activities (n=65), highlighting the importance of networking for policy-related professional development. Additionally, the policy area has a significant number of RM networks (n=69), underscoring the critical role of networks in this domain. Overall, these areas show considerable numbers of networking activities and RM networks, reflecting the importance of community development and collaboration in these domains. The higher number of opportunities in pre-award and post-award is consistent with survey data from the RM community, such as the [RAAAP survey](#) and the survey developed within WP1 of the RM-ROADMAP project, which indicate that these areas employ a larger number of Research Managers.

Innovation (n=159) and Impact (n=147) also show a high number of professional development opportunities. Training activities are particularly prominent in these areas, with impact (n=70) and innovation (n=57) leading the way. The substantial presence of RM networks relating to both impact (n=36) and innovation (n=62) further underscores the collaborative nature of these fields. Similarly, the policy area (n=179) and science communication (n=116) have a notable number of opportunities, with a strong emphasis on training and networking activities. Policy (n=65) and science communication (n=52) have the highest number of training activities, highlighting the focus on enhancing the skills and knowledge required to measure and effectively communicate research outcomes.

Data management (n=133) and ethics (n=121) show a balanced distribution of professional development opportunities across training, mobility, networking, and RM networks. This balance reflects the multifaceted nature of these areas and the need for a diverse set of skills and knowledge. However, lab management (n=48), research assessment (n=65), and infrastructure (n=62) have fewer professional development opportunities compared to other RM areas. This can be attributed to the specific focus of these areas, which involve a reduced number of Research Managers.

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Enhancing the availability of training and networking activities in these specialised fields can still help address the needs of professionals working in these areas.

There are exceptions to the trend where training activities dominate professional development opportunities. As mentioned before, in the areas of policy (n=179) and infrastructure (n=62), the number of RM networks is exceptionally high compared to other types of activities. Sixty-nine RM networks are policy-related, indicating strong support structures and community involvement in this field. Infrastructure, despite displaying fewer overall opportunities, still features a notable number of RM networks (n=20), highlighting the importance of these networks in facilitating professional development.

While mobility opportunities are present across all RM areas, they are generally fewer in number. Expanding mobility programs can facilitate international collaboration and the exchange of best practices, benefiting all RM areas. This is consistent with the previously noted importance given to mobility opportunities at the European and international levels, which could provide valuable resources for Research Managers in countries with limited national opportunities.

Professional Development Opportunities by Career Stage

Professional development opportunities are crucial for Research Managers at all career stages, as they address the evolving needs and challenges faced by individuals as they progress in their careers. RM 1 First Stage Research Managers often require foundational training and networking opportunities to build essential skills and professional connections. RM 2 Recognised Research Managers may need more specialised training and mobility opportunities to advance their expertise and facilitate international collaboration. RM 3 Established Research Managers typically benefit from advanced training in leadership and strategic development, while RM 4 Senior Research Managers need opportunities to share best practices and mentor emerging talent. Understanding the distribution of professional development opportunities across different career stages helps identify strengths and gaps in current support structures and ensures that Research Managers receive the appropriate resources at each stage of their career. Additionally, as career progression in the RM profession often involves moving to different areas within RM, it is essential to have opportunities that support this lateral movement. Ensuring a wide range of professional development opportunities also helps keep Research Managers motivated and engaged, promoting continuous growth and innovation within the profession.

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Figure 6 - Professional development opportunities by RM career stage

The majority of professional development opportunities (n=167) are available to Research Managers at all career stages. These training activities are designed to be adaptable and relevant to a wide range of experience levels, ensuring that all Research Managers, regardless of their career stage, can benefit from ongoing professional development. This broad approach has both positive and negative implications. On the positive side, it fosters a diverse pool of participants who can learn from each other's experiences, promoting cross-stage mentorship and a richer exchange of ideas. Additionally, it ensures that all Research Managers, regardless of their career stage, have access to essential resources and training. However, the downside is that these opportunities may not be specific enough to target particular skills development required at different career stages. For instance, the needs of an RM1 First Stage Research Manager, who is building foundational skills, differ significantly from those of an RM4 Senior Research Manager, who is focused on strategic leadership and high-level decision-making. This lack of specificity could result in missed opportunities for more tailored and impactful training, potentially leaving some Research Managers without the precise support they need to advance in their careers.

To maximise the benefits of these cross-level opportunities, designing modular training programs that can be customised based on experience level, implementing peer-learning initiatives to encourage cross-level knowledge transfer, and developing comprehensive online learning platforms accessible to all career stages would be advantageous. Furthermore, it is recommended that targeted professional development opportunities for each career stage are developed so as to address the specific needs more effectively.

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For **Non-Experienced Individuals** - those who are not yet in the Research Management profession - there are a total of 22 opportunities available, with a strong emphasis on training activities (n=19). This limited number highlights the need for more resources dedicated to supporting individuals who are yet to enter the RM profession, better preparing them for their roles. This lack of training for entering the profession has been previously identified by past studies, including reports developed by the HETFA Research Institute. These reports led to the development of the foRMAtion project (2019-2023, ERASMUS+), which aims to address this gap by creating an international course on Research Management for graduate students. This course has been developed by three universities in Europe, in Portugal, Hungary, and Romania.

The **RM1 Career Stage** represents Research Managers in the first two years of their careers, who require foundational training and networking opportunities to build essential skills and professional connections. The data indicates that there are only 12 training activities available exclusively for this stage. Training is particularly fundamental for RM1 as it lays the groundwork for understanding research/business structures and operations, and it includes responsibility for implementing and achieving results. However, the small number of targeted opportunities suggests that there may be a need for more foundational training programs to better support early-career Research Managers.

The **RM2 Career Stage** caters to Recognised Research Managers with an intermediate level of experience. These managers need more specialised training and mobility opportunities to advance their expertise and facilitate international collaboration. There are 16 training activities available exclusively for RM2, reflecting the necessity for continued professional growth and a deeper understanding of research and business operations, including monitoring the implementation of research strategies.

The **RM3 Career Stage** is for Established Research Managers who possess an advanced level of experience and require advanced training in leadership and strategic development. The data reveals only 2 training activities available exclusively for RM3, indicating a significant gap in targeted opportunities for this group. Established Research Managers need strong analytical skills and the ability to advise on strategic options, and more tailored professional development opportunities could enhance their capacity to fulfil these roles effectively.

The **RM4 Career Stage** involves Senior Research Managers with an expert level of experience, requiring opportunities to share best practices and mentor emerging talent. Through this mapping exercise, we have identified only 1 training activity available exclusively for RM4, highlighting a critical gap in support for senior-level managers. These managers need expert knowledge to develop strategic vision and make high-level strategic decisions, and the scarcity of targeted professional development opportunities could impact their ability to drive the overall success of their organisations.

Overall, the data indicates a strong emphasis on training activities across all career stages, with notable gaps in opportunities for RM3 and RM4 career stages. Addressing these gaps could enhance the professional development landscape, ensuring that Research Managers receive appropriate support throughout their careers.

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Additionally, providing a wide range of relevant professional development opportunities helps Research Managers maintain high levels of motivation and engagement, fostering continuous innovation within the profession.

It is important to note that career progression in the RM profession often involves moving to a different institution, and can involve moving to different areas within RM, making it essential to have opportunities that support lateral movement. Developing cross-functional training programs, encouraging intersectoral mobility and temporary assignments, and creating mentorship programs focusing on career transitions within RM can facilitate this lateral movement and broaden the skill sets of Research Managers.

To address gaps and shape future directions in RM professional development, several key areas require attention:

- **Pre-Entry Training:** Expanding training opportunities through joint programs, developing internship programs for students interested in RM careers, and creating a widely accepted introductory curriculum for aspiring RMs can help address the pre-entry gap.
- **Mid-Career Development:** Enhancing mid-career development by focusing on specialised training for RM2 and RM3 stages, developing programs addressing the transition from technical to managerial roles, and offering more opportunities for international exposure and collaboration would support the growth and motivation of experienced RMs.
- **Senior Leadership Support:** Supporting senior leadership may require executive programs focusing on strategic research management, establishing think tanks or advisory groups led by senior RMs to shape the future of the profession, and developing succession planning and knowledge transfer initiatives to strengthen the top tier of the RM field.

Engaging senior researchers in providing guidance and training for new professionals is also crucial. This mentorship can be enhanced through "train the trainer" programs, ensuring that senior researchers are equipped with the skills needed to effectively mentor and develop the next generation of Research Managers.

5. Challenges Encountered

The Catalogue aims to provide a snapshot of the opportunities available to RMs all over Europe as at July 2024. Assembling information at a European scale has met with several challenges, many of which are related to the methodology used for data collection, dissemination, and analysis. Some of the key challenges and considerations are:

- **Definition of Categories:** Defining the five categories of opportunities (Training, Mobility, Networking, Funding, RM Networks) posed challenges due to overlaps, which may affect how respondents understand and answer the questions. To mitigate this, we ensured the categories were clearly explained in the questionnaire. Specifically, mobility and networking can overlap substantially, but we have restricted the mobility category to formally established mobility programs (for peer learning, job shadowing, internships, etc) while networking focuses on a variety of activities aimed at sharing best practices, that may or not involve mobility and that may or may not be framed within specific programs.
- **RM Areas:** Classifying opportunities within RM areas was particularly challenging because the establishment of these areas has been ongoing throughout the project and has not yet reached a stabilised state. It is important to highlight that the RM areas identified are not exhaustive and others can be considered (e.g. management of doctoral training or Master programs).
- **Timeliness:** Since this is a timed exercise, the data can quickly become outdated. Nevertheless, the information will be displayed not only as a time-bound Catalogue but also as an online tool, which will be searchable and updatable. The decision to publish in a catalogue format was an attempt to render the information about opportunities available as early as possible within the project. Also, the Catalogue format is being used not only as a resource for Research Managers (RMs) but also to complement other sources of information collected throughout the development of the project which, combined, will be used to inform policy recommendations under the RM-ROADMAP project policy actions.
- **Data collection:** The data for the catalogue was collected using a mix of methodologies, namely desk research and an online template to be filled primarily by institutions responsible for providing the opportunities. This online template was disseminated throughout all countries in Europe. We guaranteed ample coverage of the request to fill in the online questionnaire by using three approaches: i) by previously mapping institutions known to provide training, networking, mobility or funding opportunities for RMs; ii) by engaging the RM-ROADMAP Ambassador Network (149 Ambassadors in 40 different countries); and via iii) a regular contact with Ambassadors by the members of the project team to ensure timely clarifications and problem solving.

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Despite strong dissemination efforts, the effectiveness of the dissemination of the online template in each country was different, and this has inevitably influenced the end result.

- **Sustainability:** Ensuring the information remains updated is important to maximise the time spent on the production of the Catalogue, and to render it useful for a longer period. One potential way to achieve this consists in transferring the information of the Catalogue to the online tool (as planned) and then (we would suggest) linking the data to other existing platforms (e.g. ERA Talents platform) to facilitate regular updates.

6. Conclusions

Research Managers now have, in a single place, a clear and easily accessible tool that provides a picture of funding, networking, mobility, and training opportunities available to pursue professional development, manage their career, and seek professional recognition. The Catalogue is a major output of the RM-ROADMAP project, which will now be widely disseminated to foster its uptake and use by RMs in Europe and beyond.

The data collected is also a starting point to unveil potential recommendations for action, which will have to be further substantiated with data obtained via the extensive survey deployed to the RM community within the scope of WP1 and WP2. Potential lines for future action are:

- There is a demand for **structured learning experiences** across Europe, which is being actively addressed through a variety of training programs and courses;
- There is a noticeable **underrepresentation of mobility** opportunities for RMs across Europe, which foster collaboration and the exchange of best practices, making this a potential area for growth and improvement. In particular, international mobility is important to gain cross-border experience that advance the field of research management, and so crucial for international research contexts;
- There is a noticeable **scarcity of funding** opportunities for RMs across Europe. As funding is essential to enable RMs to participate in conferences, workshops, and other activities, the lack of such opportunities may be creating obstacles to the continuous professional development and networking efforts of RMs, particularly those from institutions with limited resources. More funding opportunities specifically targeted at RMs are necessary;
- The significant presence of **RM Networks** may reflect **bottom-up proactiveness of a community** that faces limited opportunities for career progression, pointing to the need to reinforce and sustain RM networks as actors in career development;
- The dominance of professional development opportunities targeting **national** RMs is a strong signal that local support structures exist in many countries for skill development and community building for RMs. Universities and research performing organisations, as well as national RM networks play an important role;
- The fewer opportunities at **European and international levels** reveal a gap, particularly in mobility and funding opportunities, that could be further addressed in order to foster a more interconnected and well-supported professional community across Europe and beyond, to cope with increasingly complex and competitive international research environments;

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- **Geographically**, there are several differences in number and type of opportunities, showcasing a **positive correlation between countries with a higher number of RM Networks and the availability of training opportunities**. Barriers that hinder participation in career development activities should be assessed, especially in countries displaying fewer opportunities, as well as financial constraints, lack of institutional support, lack of reserved time for training, and limited access to information about the opportunities;
- The post-award and the pre-award **RM areas** stand out with the highest number of professional development opportunities, which is consistent with the fact that these areas employ a larger number of RMs. This also reflects the importance of community building and collaboration in these domains. Emergent or very specific RM areas may benefit from more career development opportunities being able to flourish and develop in the future;
- The majority of professional development opportunities are **available to Research Managers at all career stages** while substantially fewer opportunities are specific for each career level, with notable gaps in opportunities for the more senior RM3 and RM4 career stages. While it is ensured that all Research Managers, regardless of their career stage, have access to essential resources and training, the downside is that opportunities may not be specific enough to target particular skills development required at different career stages. Addressing these gaps could enhance the professional development landscape, ensuring that Research Managers receive appropriate support throughout their careers, contributing towards keeping Research Managers motivated and engaged, thereby fostering continuous innovation within the profession.

It is our belief that by showcasing what is already in place for the community will provide us with knowledge about the strengths, gaps and weaknesses in supporting RMs' career development. This, in turn, can provide the foundations for the development of future innovative training and mobility programmes, networking activities and funding schemes that are sound and relevant to the RM community. This catalogue is a starting point for a deeper analysis, recommendations, and the incorporation of findings into the overall roadmap for the Research Manager system in Europe.

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